

Index of training materials

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
Getting started with proteomics	Recording (YouTube video)	Recording of the live webinar presentation	Available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel https://youtu.be/RSrk2yqkIQo
Getting started with proteomics_slides	Slides (PDF)	PDF copy of the slides presented during the webinar	Included in this Zenodo record